

Conservation of Momentum Following From $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ and Fermat's Principle?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 23, 2023

Conservation of momentum is well-known from Newtonian mechanics and is associated with the idea of force. In fact, conservation of momentum is also applied in quantum mechanics and is considered to be a fundamental principle.

Here, we argue that in the case of a refracting photon, conservation of the component of momentum along the surface of the medium interface follows from the Lorentz invariant $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ and Fermat's Least Time Principle. In other words, there is no explicit physical notion of force in either of these expressions, but they yield conservation of momentum along the surface of the interface. (Note: the speed of the photon is c/n_1 in medium 1 and c/n_2 in medium 2.)

We argue, however, that during the time minimization process, the surface of the interface at $y=0$ cannot change, only the x variable. We suggest that implicitly this change in x seems to suggest there is no force in the x direction which may change the x -component of momentum. The x component of the speed of light changes, but we argue that a change in photon speed for one component is not necessarily the same as a change in the momentum in that direction. The velocity component of a particle with rest mass is immediately associated with its momentum component in the same direction. This follows because a particle's speed is r/t in $A = -Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$, with $A \neq 0$, while a photon's velocity follows from $A=0$, even if there is a physical dr/dt (moving mirror, interface). Thus one cannot think of photon's velocity components as linked to its momentum components in the same way as for a particle. The association only holds for the overall magnitude $E = |\mathbf{p}|c/n$ or the case of a single component, in which case the magnitude equals the value of the component.

Conservation of Momentum

Conservation of momentum is a fundamental idea appearing in Newtonian mechanics and is directly linked with force in the second law $d\mathbf{p} \text{ vector} / dt = \mathbf{F} \text{ vector}$ through action-reaction. In other words, there exists an \mathbf{F} and $-\mathbf{F}$ which add to zero so $d/dt \mathbf{p}_1 + \mathbf{p}_2 \text{ (vector)} = 0$ and overall momentum is conserved. In other words, a change in momentum is thought of physically in terms of an impulse hit.

Refraction of light may be described by $E = |\mathbf{p} \text{ incident}| c/n_1 = |\mathbf{p} \text{ refracted}| c/n_2$. In other words, the speed of light is different in each medium as is the magnitude of momentum. In (1), conservation of momentum is assumed for the momentum component parallel to the medium surface. In other words, there is no interaction or force in that direction it seems. Thus, the idea of force is needed to write:

$$|\mathbf{p} \text{ incident}| \sin(AA) = |\mathbf{p} \text{ refracted}| \sin(BB) \quad ((1))$$

Here AA and BB are the incident and refracted angles measured from the y axis with the medium lying along the x . Using $E = |\mathbf{p} \text{ incident}| c/n_1 = |\mathbf{p} \text{ refracted}| c/n_2$ yields Snell's law.

Conservation from $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ and Fermat's Principle

We ask: Is it possible to have conservation of momentum emerge without any physical notion of force? We argue that by using Fermat's Least Time Principle (no force involved) and the Lorentz invariant $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$, one may obtain conservation of momentum along the surface of the medium (i.e. the x axis).

We first note that $-Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ yields two equations for a photon. First \mathbf{r}/t vector is considered to be the velocity of a moving frame for a particle with rest mass. We keep this interpretation for a photon ($A \neq 0$), but there is no moving surface in a refraction problem with a fixed medium interface, so $A = -Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r} = -Et$. This means that E is the same for the incident and reflected ray. This assumption used above follows directly from the $A = -Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$. In the case of refraction from a moving surface, one does not have $E_{\text{incident}} = E_{\text{refracted}}$, but rather:

$$|\mathbf{p}_{\text{incident}}| \left\{ \frac{E}{|\mathbf{p}_{\text{incident}}|} + \text{unit vector} \cdot \mathbf{r} \right\} = |\mathbf{p}_{\text{refracted}}| \left\{ \frac{E}{|\mathbf{p}_{\text{refracted}}|} + \text{unit vector} \cdot \mathbf{r} \right\} \quad ((2))$$

where $E/|\mathbf{p}| = c/n$ and the unit vector is along the appropriate \mathbf{p} .

The second equation which emerges from $A = -Et + \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}$ is for $A=0$ with \mathbf{p} taken along the x axis. Then: $x/t = E/p =$ the speed of a photon. We assume $E = pc/n$.

Next, we apply Fermat's least time principle for a surface along the x axis. Light travels from a $y=B, x=0$ point to $y=0, x=L$ and then refracts to $y=-B, x=L$. Fermat's principle states that time must be minimized. Time may be written as:

$$T_1 + t_2 = n_1/c \sqrt{B^2 + x^2} + n_2/c \sqrt{B^2 + (L-x)^2} \quad ((3))$$

$$d/dt (t_1 + t_2) = 0 \text{ to minimize so one actually uses } d/dx \text{ on } ((3)) \text{ to obtain: } n_1 \frac{x}{\sqrt{B^2 + x^2}} - n_2 \frac{(L-x)}{\sqrt{B^2 + (L-x)^2}} \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is equivalent to $\sin(AA) / \sin(BB) = n_2/n_1$ where AA is the incident angle measured from the y axis and BB the refracted, also measured from the y axis.

((4)) is Snell's law. At this point there is no conservation of momentum. Using $E_{\text{incident}} = E_{\text{refracted}}$ means that:

$$|\mathbf{p}_{\text{incident}}| c/n_1 = |\mathbf{p}_{\text{refracted}}| c/n_2 \text{ or } n_2/n_1 = |\mathbf{p}_{\text{refracted}}| / |\mathbf{p}_{\text{incident}}| = \sin(AA) / \sin(BB)$$

$$\text{Thus: } |\mathbf{p}_{\text{refracted}}| \sin(BB) = |\mathbf{p}_{\text{incident}}| \sin(AA) \quad ((5))$$

((5)), however, represents the conservation of momentum along the x-axis, without any notion of force being introduced.

It seems that it is Fermat's principle of least time which singles out the x-component of momentum because it introduces $\sin(AA)$ and $\sin(BB)$, linking them directly to n_2/n_1 which in turn is linked to $|p_{\text{incident}}|$ and $|p_{\text{refracted}}|$.

Why should the minimization of time have anything to do with momentum conservation? Momentum conservation is usually associated with force, i.e. $F-F=0$ for action-reaction. The medium interface is fixed at $y=0$, so in the Fermat's least time principle, one may only shift the x point (through d/dx) as B, $-B$ and $(0,L)$ are fixed. The fact that one may freely shift the x point to minimize time suggests there is nothing hindering such x movement, i.e. no force in that direction. This suggests force acts in the y direction. If there is no force in the x direction, there should be conservation of the x component of momentum in this direction.. Thus, we argue that the free movement of x in the time minimization process seems to be already associated with the idea of a lack of force in this direction which implies no change in momentum in this direction.

The component of velocity in the x direction changes from $c/n_1 \sin(AA)$ to $c/n_2 \sin(BB)$, but it has already been noted that this speed of light is not like the velocity of a particle with rest mass. For such a particle, its change in a velocity component means a change in the corresponding momentum component, but not for light. The x-component of the speed of light may change without $p(x)$ changing because the speed of light follows from $A=0 = -Et + p \cdot r$, whereas the speed of a particle is associated with dr/dt vector and $A \neq 0$. For light, there is a direct relationship between $|p|$ and the magnitude of velocity, i.e. $E=|p| c/n$. This carries over to p in one direction, such as x, but not to 3 directions, whereas for a particle with rest mass, $p(x)=m_0 v(x)$, $p(y)=m_0 v(y)$, $p(z)=m_0 v(z)$, nonrelativistically. Relativistically m_0 is replaced with $m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$

These results may be generalized for reflection or refraction from a mirror or interface along x moving in the y direction. Again $p(x)$ (the x-component of momentum) is conserved.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that conservation of momentum, which in Newtonian mechanics, is associated with the action-reaction cancellation of forces, may arise without any explicit reference to force. We consider refraction from a fixed interface along x at $y=0$. The Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + p \cdot r$ ensures that $E_{\text{incident}} = E_{\text{reflected}}$. The speed of light emerges from $A=0$, whereas a particle's velocity is linked to a moving frame, i.e. r/t vector.

Here r/t vector=0 for a fixed interface of two media. The speed of light has both its x and y components change during refraction. Fermat's principle of minimization of time considers the interface fixed at $y=0$. There is no variation of y, only x for a light ray which starts at $x=0, y=B$, hits the interface at $y=0$ and moves to $x=-B, y=L$. We suggest that the freedom of moving x in this minimization of time problem implicitly assumes no force in the x-direction and thus leads to a conservation of momentum in the x-direction. Thus, even though one states that one minimizes time, it is a minimization subject to the constraint that the surface of the interface cannot be varied, only x, because there nothing stopping one from shifting the x point.

It is interesting to note that for refraction for a ray moving along the y-axis, there is no $p(x)$ component, but $p(y)$ physically changes according to $p(y)(\text{incident}) c/n_1 = p(y) (\text{refracted}) c/n_2$. Thus the idea that $p(x)$ is the same for the incident and refracted ray holds even in this case.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Snell%27s_law